

The Group Composition, Status and Richness of The Avian Life In And Around Lilkee Beed of Churu, Rajasthan (India)

Paper Id : 19074 Submission Date : 2024-07-10 Acceptance Date : 2024-07-18 Publication Date : 2024-07-22
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13283311

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Abstract The Churu district of Rajasthan is located in a semi-arid region that is part of the great Thar Desert. From January to December 2023, the bird diversity in and around Lilkee Beed of Churu was examined. Birds were noted to be present in the morning, midday, and evening. 32 families and 70 bird species were identified during the study period. Every species was terrestrial. Furthermore, 64 resident species, 3 occasional visitors, and 3 winter visitors were observed. The Accipitridae, Columbidae, and Alaudidae were the three leading families in the research area based on the relative diversity index (RD). Globally, two species of the Falconidae family and one species of Accipitridae are classified as near threatened. One of the Accipitridae species is classified as endangered. Each omnivorous and insectivorous group accounted for 29% of the guild (group composition) separately, with carnivorous groups following at 27%, granivorous at 11%, granivorous and frugivorous at 3%, and nectarivorous at 1%. The study delivers a general overview of the bird diversity in and around Lilkee Beed.

Keywords Avian Diversity, Lilkee Beed, Rajasthan, Guild, IUCN Red List.

Introduction One of the key components of total biodiversity is avian variety. Birds are found in practically every kind of environment on the planet and they play a crucial role for numerous food chains. There are around 1800 genera and 9702 species of birds in the world (Sibley and Monroe, 1990). Over 13% of the world's bird species, or roughly 1375 species, are found in the Indian subcontinent out of the world's more than 9000 species (Grimmett et al., 2016). The diversity of organisms present within the area is a reflection of the biological diversity of that specific region. Each species plays a unique role in an ecosystem, making them unique units of diversity.

Objective of study The goal of the current study is to evaluate the variety of bird species found in and around the Lilkee beed. Along with the guild composition, an attempt has also been made to determine the status of birds in the area. This study will contribute to a reservoir of knowledge regarding the region's avian diversity. This will be in addition to the national and international data as well. The information produced by this investigation will also be used as a benchmark in the future to develop more effective conservation plans for bird diversity.

Review of Literature A region's entire collection of genes, species, and ecosystems is reflected in its name, biodiversity. In Rajasthan, the district Bharatpur, South Rajasthan, Jodhpur, Jaisalmer, Jhunjhunu and Churu have been the primary sites for avian fauna studies (Satpal et al., 2024, Bhatnagar et al., 2008, 2011, Bhatnagar and Shekhawat, 2014; Chhangani, 2002; Koli et al., 2011; Sangha and Devarshi, 2006; Sharma, A. K. and Singh, K. R., 1989;

Sharma and Tehsin, 1994). There have been some attempts to document the avifaunal richness of the Churu area, primarily the Tal Chhapar Sanctuary, even though the Lilkee beed in Rajasthan's Churu district has not been thoroughly explored. Thus, documenting the variety of birds in and around Lilkee beed is the main objective of current study. The study region is a perfect habitat for a wide range of birds because of its vegetation and agricultural areas. Churu district of Rajasthan is situated in the northwest of the state of Rajasthan. *Ziziphus mauritiana* (ber), *Prosopis cineraria* (khejri), *Capparis decidua* (Ker), *Tecomella undulata* (rohida), *Salvadora oleoides* (meethi-jaal) and *Acacia nilotica* (kikar) are a few of the species that are commonly found across the research region. The study region has three distinct seasons: summer (March to July), winter (November to February), and monsoon (August to October). While the lowest temperature in the winter is approximately 0°C, the summer months can see temperatures as high as 47°C.

Main Text **Study area**

A protected area the Lilkee Beed (also called Beed Rajgarh) of Churu in Rajasthan's Thar Desert is around 30 kilometers to the northwest from Rajgarh tehsil, while from the district headquarters it is 67 km toward north. Lilkee beed is located at 28°76' N 75°21' E (Google map@2024). Lilkee beed is spread in about 1100 hectares or 4500 Bighaas. There are 20 kund (tanka) and 18 artificial ponds for wildlife to use as water sources. Around Lilkee beed is an eighteen-kilometer wall made of bricks that ranges in height from 5 to 7 feet. Up to 15 kilometers may be observed from the tall mound (Hathi Tilla) of Lilkee beed. Some of the villages close to Lilkee beed of Churu are Bhambhada, Kasoombi, Jodhawas, Jothada, Ghasla, Rojhani, and Mithdi patta dadrewa. Lilkee Beed in Churu is facing significant ecological challenges, including unchecked herbivore population, meteorological shocks, and agricultural field raids. Preserving ecological balance is crucial (Mehra B. L. and Satpal, 2019).

Fig1. A- Map of Rajasthan, B- Map of Churu, C- Map of Lilkee beed of Churu

Methodology From January 2023 to December 2023, the study was carried out in and around the Lilkee beed at several locations, such as those close to water sources, feeding zones, nesting areas, resting areas, and areas with dense vegetation. Field surveys using the point counts approach were conducted in the morning, midday, and evening at these often visited places. Two observers recorded the species of birds present at each study site independently. To aid in further identification, they took images of the birds with Canon cameras. The various bird species were identified using standard reference books (Amano Samarpan 2006, Grimmett et al., 2016 and Ali & Ripley, 2003). Three groups of birds were identified based on their residential status- residents, winter visitors and occasional visitors. Birds that were routinely spotted in the study region were classified as residential, while species that were only observed once or twice during the study period were classified as occasionally visitors. Winter visitors are those birds that have only been seen in the winter. The advanced transect approach maintains a constant transect length of 1500 meters while varying the width length based on the survey area. For example, the width in a dense area was 15 meters and in other open fields it was 50 meters. Over the course of the study period, eighteen transects were completed. The relative abundance of each bird species was used to compute the encounter rate, which

was then expressed as the number of bird species observed or traveled (km). The following formula was used to determine relative diversity (RD):

$$RD = \text{Number of species in a family} / \text{Total number of species} \times 100$$

Analysis

Table1. Guild (Group Composition), Status and Richness of Bird Fauna Observed in and Around Lilkee Beed

No. of Species	Scientific Name	English Name	IUCN*	Status	Guild**
Accipitridae					
1	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Black kite	LC	R	Carnivorous
2	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	Black-shouldered kite	LC	R	Omnivorous
3	<i>Circus macrourus</i>	Pallid harrier	NT	R	Carnivorous
4	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	Shikra	LC	R	Carnivorous
5	<i>Circaetus gallicus</i>	Short-toed snake eagle	LC	R	Carnivorous
6	<i>Aquila nipalensis</i>	Steppe eagle	EN	R	Carnivorous
7	<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>	Wastern marsh harrier	LC	OV	Carnivorous
Alaudidae					
8	<i>Calandrella brachydactyla</i>	Greater short-toed lark	LC	WV	Omnivorous
9	<i>Ammomanes phoenicurus</i>	Rufous tailed lark	LC	WV	Omnivorous
10	<i>Eremopterix grisea</i>	Ashy-crowned sparrow lark	LC	OV	Omnivorous
11	<i>Mirafra erythroptera</i>	Indian bush lark	LC	R	Omnivorous
12	<i>Alauda gulgula</i>	Oriental sky lark	LC	R	Insectivorous
Alcedinidae					
13	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	White throated kingfisher	LC	R	Carnivorous
Apodidae					
14	<i>Apus affinis</i>	House swift	LC	R	Insectivorous
15	<i>Cypsiurus balasiensis</i>	Asian Palm-Swift	LC	R	Insectivorous
Ardeidae					
16	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	Indian pond heron	LC	R	Carnivorous
17	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle egret	LC	R	Carnivorous
18	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Little egret	LC	R	Carnivorous
19	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Gray heron	LC	R	Carnivorous
Bucerotidae					

20	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i>	Indian Grey Hornbill	LC	R	Omnivorous
Charadriidae					
21	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	Red-wattled lapwing	LC	R	Insectivorous
Columbidae					
22	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Eurasian collared-dove	LC	R	Granivorous
23	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	Indian ring-dove	LC	R	Granivorous
24	<i>Streptopelia senegalensis</i>	Laughing dove	LC	R	Granivorous
25	<i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i>	Red collared dove	LC	R	Granivorous
26	<i>Columba livia</i>	Rock pigeon	LC	R	Granivorous
Coraciidae					
27	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	Indian roller	LC	R	Carnivorous
Corvidae					
28	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	House crow	LC	R	Carnivorous
29	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	Rufous treepie	LC	R	Carnivorous
30	<i>Corvus culminates</i>	Indian jungle crow	LC	R	Carnivorous
Cuculidae					
31	<i>Eudynamys scolopacea</i>	Asian koel	LC	R	Omnivorous
32	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	Greater Coucal	LC	R	Omnivorous
33	<i>Hierococcyx varius</i>	Common Hawk-Cuckoo	LC	R	Omnivorous
Dicruridae					
34	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	Black drongo	LC	R	Insectivorous
Estrildidae					
35	<i>Lonchura malabarica</i>	Indian silver bill	LC	R	Omnivorous
Falconidae					
36	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	Eurasian kestrel	LC	R	Carnivorous
37	<i>Falco chicquera</i>	Red-necked Falcon	NT	R	Carnivorous
38	<i>Falco jugger</i>	Laggar Falcon	NT	R	Carnivorous
Laniidae					
39	<i>Lanius excubitor</i>	Great grey shrike	LC	R	Insectivorous
40	<i>Lanius vittatus</i>	bay-backed shrike	LC	R	Insectivorous
Leiothrichidae					
41	<i>Argya malcolmi</i>	Large gray babbler	LC	R	Insectivorous
Meropidae					
42	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Green bee-eater	LC	R	Insectivorous

43	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	Blue-tailed bee-eater	LC	R	Insectivorous
44	<i>Merops persicus</i>	Blue-cheeked Bee-eater	LC	R	Insectivorous
Motacillidae					
45	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	White wagtail	LC	R	Insectivorous
Muscicapidae					
46	<i>Copsychus fulicatus</i>	Indian robin	LC	R	Insectivorous
47	<i>Ficedula parva</i>	Red-breasted Flycatcher	LC	R	Insectivorous
Nectariniidae					
48	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	Purple sunbird	LC	R	Nectarivorous
Passeridae					
49	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House sparrow	LC	R	Granivorous
50	<i>Passer pyrrhonotus</i>	Sind Sparrow	LC	R	Granivorous
51	<i>Gymnoris xanthocollis</i>	Yellow-throated Sparrow	LC	R	Granivorous
Phasianidae					
52	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	Indian peafowl	LC	R	Omnivorous
53	<i>Francolinus pondicerianus</i>	Gray francolin	LC	R	Omnivorous
54	<i>Francolinus francolinus</i>	Black francolin	LC	R	Omnivorous
Picidae					
55	<i>Dendrocopos mahrattensis</i>	Yellow crowned woodpecker	LC	R	Insectivorous
56	<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>	Black-rumped flameback	LC	R	Insectivorous
Ploceidae					
57	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	Baya weaver	LC	R	Omnivorous
Podicipedidae					
58	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	Little Grebe	LC	OV	Carnivorous
Psittacidae					
59	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Rose-ringed parakeet	LC	R	Granivorous & Frugivorous
60	<i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	Plum headed parakeet	LC	R	Granivorous & Frugivorous
Pycnonotidae					
61	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	Red-vented Bulbul	LC	R	Omnivorous
62	<i>Pycnonotus leucotis</i>	White eared bulbul	LC	R	Omnivorous
Strigidae					
63	<i>Athene brama</i>	Spotted owl	LC	R	Insectivorous

Sturnidae					
64	<i>Acridotheres ginginianus</i>	Bank myna	LC	R	Omnivorous
65	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	Common myna	LC	R	Omnivorous
66	<i>Sturnus pagodarum</i>	Brahminy starling	LC	R	Omnivorous
67	<i>Sturnus contra</i>	Asian pied starling	LC	R	Omnivorous
Sylviidae					
68	<i>Sylvia curruca</i>	Lesser white throat	LC	WV	Insectivorous
Threskiornithidae					
69	<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	Black ibis	LC	R	Insectivorous
Upupidae					
70	<i>Upupa epops</i>	Common hoopoe	LC	R	Insectivorous

Status: R= resident, WV= winter visitor, OV= occasionally visitor,

International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN) categories: LC= least concern; NT= near threatened; EN= endangered

* The information based on the IUCN Red List (IUCN 2023-1)

** Guild status (mostly) in Table 1 is from Cornell Lab of Ornithology 2024

Fig 2. Relative diversity among all avian families in and around Lilkee Beed of Churu, Rajasthan

Fig 3. The residential status of avian fauna in and around Lilkee Beed of Churu, Rajasthan

Fig 4. Guild based classification of avian fauna in and around Lilkee Beed of Churu, Rajasthan

1. *Ardeola grayii*

2. *Bubulcus ibis*

3. *Cinnyris asiaticus*

4. *Argya malcolmi*

5. *Coracias benghalensis*

6. *Halcyon smyrnensis*

7. *Milvis migrans*

8. *Passer domesticus*

9. *Lanius excubitor*

10. *Pavo cristatus*

11. *Pycnonotus cafer*

12. *Centropus sinensis*

13. *Merops orientalis*

14. *Streptopelia capicola*

15. *Sturnus pagodarum*

16. *Upupa epops*

17. *Vanellus indicus*

Conclusion Over the course of the study, 70 different kinds of birds were observed in and around Lilkee Beed of Churu, as shown in Table 1. There is a single Accipitridae species that is endangered. The International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources has classified two species of Falconidae and one species of Accipitridae as globally near threatened (IUCN). The 66 species that survive here are least concern species. Based on the results of the current study, the Lilkee beed was home to 91.42% of resident species, 4.29% of occasional visits, and 4.29% of winter visitors out of 70 bird species (Figure 3). The guild's composition was 29% with omnivorous birds, 29% insectivorous birds, 27% carnivorous birds, 11% granivorous birds, 3% granivorous & frugivorous birds, and 1% nectarivorous birds (Pie chart Figure 4). Thirty-two families were seen in and

around the beed during the study period. The Accipitridae was the dominant family in the research area, as shown by the Relative Diversity Index (RD) value of 10. The RD values of 7.14 for Columbidae and Alaudidae were same (Figure 2). Every species is terrestrial in this area. In addition, three species visit occasionally, three species visited over the winter, and 64 species are resident species that have persisted here.

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